

Agronomic and Economic Evaluation of Compound Fertilizer Application on Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* L.)

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ABSTRACT

*Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* L.) is a high-value vegetable crop that requires balanced nutrient management to achieve optimal growth and yield. This study aimed to evaluate the agronomic and economic effectiveness of a compound fertilizer containing 21% N, 17% P₂O₅, and 17% K₂O on cabbage production. The experiment was conducted using a randomized complete block design with seven fertilization treatments, including a control, a reference NPK treatment, and five levels of compound fertilizer (0.5 to 1.5 recommended doses), each replicated four times. Observations included plant height, leaf number, yield per plant, yield per plot, and yield per hectare. Statistical analysis was performed using ANOVA and Duncan's Multiple Range Test at a 5% significance level, while economic analysis was based on profit and benefit-cost ratio (R/C). The results showed that the 1.0 dose of compound fertilizer significantly improved plant height at 3 and 4 weeks after transplanting, increased leaf number at 5 weeks, and produced the highest yield per plant (1.92 kg), per plot (43.8 kg), and per hectare (17,500 kg). This treatment also demonstrated the highest relative agronomic effectiveness (139%) and economic viability, with an R/C ratio of 2.23 and a profit of IDR 14,487,900. Based on these findings, the recommended application rate for cabbage is 211 kg/ha of compound fertilizer, applied one week after transplanting. The study concludes that compound fertilizer is both agronomically effective and economically profitable for cabbage cultivation under the tested conditions.*

Keywords: agronomic effectiveness, cabbage cultivation, compound fertilizer, economic analysis, nutrient management

INTRODUCTION

Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* L.) is one of the most important leafy vegetable crops cultivated in Indonesia and many other parts of the world. It is widely consumed due to its high nutritional value, including vitamins, minerals, and dietary fiber, and it also serves as a significant source of income for smallholder farmers (Cui et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2019). To achieve optimal growth and high yields, cabbage requires a balanced and adequate supply of essential nutrients, particularly nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) (Yfantopoulos et al., 2024). These macronutrients play critical roles in plant physiological processes such as cell division, photosynthesis, energy transfer, and enzyme activation (Bhattarai et al., 2023; Easmin et al., 2009).

In modern agricultural systems, inorganic fertilizers are commonly used to meet the nutrient demands of crops. However, the efficiency of these fertilizers depends not only on their chemical composition but also on the method and timing of application (Xu et al., 2022; Pan et al., 2025). Compound fertilizers, which contain a balanced ratio of N, P₂O₅, and K₂O in a single formulation, offer several advantages over conventional single-nutrient fertilizers (Pan et al., 2025; Rajendran et al., 2021). These include ease of application, reduced labor, and the potential for improved nutrient use efficiency. Despite these advantages, the effectiveness of compound fertilizers must be evaluated under specific agroecological conditions to determine their suitability and cost-effectiveness for local farming systems (Sun et al., 2023; Okey-Onyesolu et al., 2021).

Compound fertilizer, which contains 21% N, 17% P₂O₅, and 17% K₂O, has been introduced as a potential alternative to traditional fertilization practices in vegetable production. However, limited information is available regarding its performance on cabbage under field conditions in Indonesia. Therefore, it is essential to assess both the agronomic and economic effectiveness of this fertilizer to provide evidence-based recommendations for farmers.

This study was conducted to evaluate the response of cabbage to different application rates of compound fertilizer. The objectives were to (1) assess the effects of fertilizer dosage on plant growth parameters such as height and leaf number, (2) determine the impact on yield components including yield per plant, per plot, and per hectare, (3) calculate the relative agronomic effectiveness compared to standard fertilization practices, and (4) analyze the economic feasibility of each treatment using farm business analysis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The materials used in this study included cabbage seeds, the compound fertilizer being tested for its effectiveness, urea, SP-36, and KCl. The tested compound fertilizer contained 21% nitrogen (N), 17% phosphorus pentoxide (P₂O₅), and 17% potassium oxide (K₂O). The tools used included cultivation equipment (hoe, hand cultivator, sprayer), sample markers, measuring tape, and a digital scale. Data processing was conducted using a computer and the SAS statistical analysis software.

Methods

The experiment was arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD). The treatments consisted of seven fertilization levels: no NPK fertilization (P0), reference NPK fertilization (P1), 0.5 dose of compound fertilizer (P2), 0.75 dose (P3), 1 dose (P4), 1.25 dose (P5), and 1.5 dose (P6). The experiment was replicated four times, resulting in 28 experimental units. Each unit was a plot of land measuring 25 m². Detailed treatment descriptions are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Details of Compound Fertilizer Treatments

Treatment	Dosage of Compound Fertilizer (kg/ha)	Dosage of Urea (kg/ha)	Dosage of KCl (kg/ha)	Dosage of SP-36 (kg/ha)
Control	-	-	-	-
Reference	-	200	100	100
0.5 dose of compound fertilizer	105	51	20	-
0.75 dose of compound fertilizer	158	76	30	-
1.0 dose of compound fertilizer	211	102	40	-
1.25 dose of compound fertilizer	264	127	50	-
1.5 dose of compound fertilizer	316	153	60	-

Field Preparation and Crop Management

The field was thoroughly prepared by double hoeing until ready for planting. The second hoeing was followed by the construction of raised beds, each 1 meter wide and 5 meters long, with 50 cm spacing between beds. Each experimental unit consisted of five raised beds. Seedlings were transplanted at 21 days after sowing, with one seedling per planting hole. The planting distance was 60 cm × 40 cm, with one plant per hole. Compound fertilizer was applied according to the treatment dosage one week after transplanting. Pest and disease control was carried out as needed using limited pesticide applications based on infestation levels.

Data Collection

Plant growth observations included plant height and leaf number, measured on five randomly selected sample plants. Yield and yield components included yield per plant, yield per plot, and yield per hectare, which was calculated from plot yield.

Statistical Analysis and Economic Evaluation

Data were statistically analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at a 5% significance level. Farm business analysis was conducted using economic evaluation variables, including profit and the benefit-cost ratio (R/C). The fertilizer was considered technically effective if its treatment

was statistically equivalent to or better than the reference treatment or control at the 5% significance level. Economic effectiveness was determined based on whether the farm business analysis showed profitability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results

Effect of Compound Fertilizer on Cabbage Growth

Compound fertilizer treatments significantly affected cabbage plant height at 3 and 4 weeks after transplanting (WAT), but no significant differences were observed at 5 and 6 WAT (Table 2). The 0.5-dose treatment resulted in greater plant height than the control at 3 WAT. The 1.0-dose treatment produced the tallest plants at 4 WAT compared to the control. However, no significant differences in plant height were observed among treatments at 5 and 6 WAT.

Table 2. Effect of Compound Fertilizer Application on Cabbage Plant Height

Treatment	Plant Height (cm)			
	3 WAT	4 WAT	5 WAT	6 WAT
Control	18.5b	23.7b	28.4a	30.0a
Reference	19.2ab	25.2ab	28.9a	31.7a
0.5 dose of compound fertilizer	19.4a	25.6ab	28.9a	31.6a
0.75 dose of compound fertilizer	19.3ab	25.5ab	28.4a	29.0a
1.0 dose of compound fertilizer	18.9ab	25.9a	28.9a	29.9a
1.25 dose of compound fertilizer	19.3ab	24.8ab	28.0a	31.5a
1.5 dose of compound fertilizer	18.9ab	24.8ab	28.7a	30.9a

Note: Values in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at the 5% significance level.

Several compound fertilizer doses significantly influenced leaf number at 5 WAT, while no differences were found at 3, 4, and 6 WAT compared to the control and reference treatments (Table 3). Treatments with 0.5 to 1.5 doses resulted in a higher leaf count than the control at 5 WAT.

Table 3. Effect of Compound Fertilizer Application on the Number of Cabbage Leaves

Treatment	Leaf Number			
	3 WAT	4 WAT	5 WAT	6 WAT
Control	7.5a	10.3a	13.3b	21.7a
Reference	7.5a	10.9a	14.1a	22.3a
0.5 dose of compound fertilizer	7.7a	10.6a	14.4a	22.3a
0.75 dose of compound fertilizer	7.5a	10.6a	14.2a	22.1a
1.0 dose of compound fertilizer	7.5a	11.0a	14.8a	22.7a
1.25 dose of compound fertilizer	7.5a	10.3a	14.2a	22.4a
1.5 dose of compound fertilizer	7.5a	10.9a	14.4a	21.8a

Note: Values in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at the 5% significance level.

Effect of Compound Fertilizer on Cabbage Yield

Compound fertilizer application significantly affected yield per plant (Table 4). Different doses produced varying yield responses. The 1.0-dose treatment yielded the highest cabbage weight per plant (1.92 kg), significantly higher than the control (1.03 kg) and reference (1.72 kg) treatments, representing increases of 86.4% and 11.6%, respectively.

Table 4. Effect of Compound Fertilizer Application on Cabbage Yield

Treatment	Yield per plant (g)	Yield per plot (kg)	Yield per ha (kg/ha)
Control	1030.0e	24.3e	9700e
Reference	1720.0b	38.3c	15300c
0.5 dose of compound fertilizer	1545.0d	37.8dc	15100dc
0.75 dose of compound fertilizer	1540.0d	37.0d	14800d
1.0 dose of compound fertilizer	1920.0a	43.8a	17500a
1.25 dose of compound fertilizer	1710.0b	36.8d	14700d
1.5 dose of compound fertilizer	1660.0c	41.8b	16700b

Note: Values in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at the 5% significance level.

Compound fertilizer also significantly influenced yield per plot and yield per hectare (Table 4). The 1.0-dose treatment produced the highest yield per plot (43.8 kg), compared to 24.3 kg (control) and 38.3 kg (reference). Similarly, the 1.0-dose treatment resulted in the highest yield per hectare, consistent with the positive correlation between yield per plant, per plot, and per hectare.

Relative Agronomic Effectiveness

Relative agronomic effectiveness is a key indicator of fertilizer performance. A fertilizer is considered agronomically effective if its relative effectiveness exceeds 100%, indicating a greater yield increase than that achieved by the reference fertilizer compared to the control. The analysis results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Relative Agronomic Effectiveness of Compound Fertilizer Treatments

Treatment	Relative Agronomic Effectiveness (%)
Control	-
Reference	-
0.5 dose of compound fertilizer	96
0.75 dose of compound fertilizer	91
1.0 dose of compound fertilizer	139
1.25 dose of compound fertilizer	89
1.5 dose of compound fertilizer	125

The 1.0 and 1.5-dose treatments showed relative agronomic effectiveness values of 139% and 125%, respectively. The 1.0-dose treatment was the most effective, increasing yield by 1.39 times compared to the yield improvement from the reference fertilizer.

Farm Business Analysis

Economic effectiveness was evaluated using profit and the benefit-cost ratio (R/C). These indicators assess the economic feasibility of the farming practice. Results of the farm business analysis for various treatments are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Farm Business Analysis of Compound Fertilizer Effectiveness Treatments

Treatment	Cost (Rp)	Revenue (Rp)	Benefit (Rp)	R/C
Control	9,425,000	14,550,000	5,125,000	1.54
Reference	12,035,000	22,950,000	10,915,000	1.91
0.5 dose of compound fertilizer	10,589,800	22,650,000	12,060,200	2.14
0.75 dose of compound fertilizer	11,174,800	22,200,000	11,025,200	1.99
1.0 dose of compound fertilizer	11,762,100	26,250,000	14,487,900	2.23
1.25 dose of compound fertilizer	12,347,100	22,050,000	9,702,900	1.79
1.5 dose of compound fertilizer	12,926,900	25,050,000	12,123,100	1.94

A fertilizer is considered economically viable if the R/C ratio exceeds 1. Several compound fertilizer treatments had R/C ratios > 1, indicating profitability for farmers. The 1.0-dose treatment had the highest R/C ratio (2.23), generating a profit of IDR 14,487,900.

Discussion

Compound fertilizer application improved cabbage growth, including plant height (3 and 4 WAT), leaf number (5 WAT), yield per plant, per plot, and per hectare. While early growth parameters showed significant differences, later growth stages did not. However, yield components consistently showed positive responses. The 1.0-dose treatment increased yield per plant by 86.4% and 11.6% compared to the control and reference treatments, respectively. Similarly, yield per plot and per hectare increased by 80.2% and 14.4%.

Nitrogen supplied through compound fertilizers is crucial for plant growth as it is transformed by soil bacteria into ammonium and nitrate through processes known as ammonification and nitrification (Schimel & Bennett, 2004). This transformation is essential for the availability of nitrogen and plays a significant role in chlorophyll synthesis and overall plant health (Ye et al., 2022). A deficiency in nitrogen can lead to stunted growth, thin stems, lodging, and narrow leaves (Ye et al., 2022).

Phosphorus, another vital nutrient, is essential in various metabolic processes, including carbohydrate formation and chloroplast activity, which significantly impact plant health and productivity (Ren et al., 2024). The role of phosphorus in energy

transfer mechanisms, such as ATP production, supports numerous cellular functions integral to plant development (Li et al., 2021).

Additionally, potassium is fundamental in regulating enzyme activities necessary for stomatal function and water regulation within the plant. A deficiency in potassium can lead to impaired carbohydrate translocation and issues with nitrogen metabolism, increasing plants' vulnerability to lodging and fungal infections (Davies-Barnard & Friedlingstein, 2020). Thus, the availability of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium is critical not only for enhancing plant growth but also for maintaining plant health and maximizing yield.

The effectiveness of compound fertilizer was evident both agronomically and economically. The 1.0-dose treatment had the highest agronomic effectiveness (139%) and economic viability, with the highest R/C ratio and profit.

CONCLUSION

The results of the field experiment demonstrated that the 1.0 dose of compound fertilizer produced superior yield components compared to both the control and reference treatments. This treatment was proven to be both agronomically and economically effective, with an R/C ratio of 2.23 and a profit of IDR 14,487,900. The field evaluation confirmed that the compound fertilizer is agronomically effective and economically profitable. The recommended dosage for cabbage cultivation is 211 kg/ha per application, applied one week after transplanting.

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